

Studies on Sulphur and Alkali Sulphides as Emulsifying Agents

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The work has been extended to the emulsions of sulphur and alkali sulphides which are described as good and efficient insecticides as well as acaricides and fungicides.

SULPHUR and a number of its inorganic compounds function both as insecticides, as well as acaricides, and fungicides, and, although first used as insecticides, now are probably more widely used to destroy fungi.

The chemistry of the sulphur derivatives which are among the most powerful of insecticides has been discussed by Streeter and Rankin¹², and Goodhue⁹; Wilcoxon and McCallan³, White¹³ and Volck¹⁴.

One of the most important group of compounds used as insecticides and fungicides includes the polysulphides of the alkali metals, including ammonia. These materials, although were used first as acaricides and insecticides, are now most widely used as fungicides.

The sulphides of potassium, liver of sulphur and sodium have along been used as fungicides and insecticides, either as a solution of the salts alone or as a home made preparation. This is prepared by boiling sulphur and an alkali hydroxide, together in a manner similar to the preparation of lime sulphur solutions; although the reaction between sodium and potassium hydroxides and sulphur will proceed without the addition of heat. Such a preparation of sodium hydroxide (lye) and sulphur is described by Lodeman² and Haywood⁷.

Abbott, Culver and Morgan¹⁵ tested a dried preparation of "sodium sulphur" and found that, while it gave results similar to dried lime sulphur, it was not particularly effective against San Jose Scale.

In continuation with the previous work⁸, the work has been further extended to the study of sulphur and alkali sulphides which have been listed in the literature as good insecticides, as well as acaricides and fungicides in literature.

Experimental

The gums were purified by the methods as described by Mukherjee and Shukla¹⁰ in their earlier work on gums. The emulsions were prepared at 30° by King and Mukherjee's¹ method using fixed concentration of the alkali sulphides alone and then by adding fixed amounts of gums keeping the ratio of the oil (olive) to water as 30:70 so that the

emulsions produced were not very viscous and could be sprayed easily for practical purposes. The size frequency analysis was done immediately and on regular intervals of time on specific surfaces of these emulsions applying the theory of least squares as described by Mukherjee and Shukla^{10,11}.

Results and Discussions

A large number of olive oil in water emulsions stabilised by fixed amount of different forms of sulphur (precipitated and sublimed) and some alkali sulphides were made. Size frequency analysis was done on them immediately after preparation and at different intervals of time thereafter.

In case of sulphur the stable emulsions were not possible. The summarised results of Tables 1 and 2 are all concerning the emulsions of alkali sulphides. It can be seen that in general sodium sulphide stabilised emulsions and emulsions produced by the combinations of this substance with gums dhak, bel and katira are stabler than potassium sulphide emulsions, produced with single substance and combination of this substance with the gums. The stability coefficient values in case of sodium sulphide can be arranged in the order: bel gum > dhak gum > sodium sulphide alone > katira gum. This order remains unaltered, in case of potassium sulphide, stabilised emulsions no. 113, 112, 111 and 114 as can be seen from the stability coefficient values of these emulsions in Table 2, although emulsions stabilised with sodium sulphide are somewhat more stable.

So far as calculated interfacial area values and graphically determined interfacial area values are concerned, it can be ascertained from Tables 1 and 2 respectively, that these have got higher values in case of potassium sulphide stabilised emulsions, in comparison to the sodium sulphide emulsions individually as well as when used in combination with different Indian gums. This indicates that the emulsions produced by potassium sulphide and by the combination of this substance with different gums are finer as compared to their counterpart emulsions stabilised by sodium sulphide.

TABLE 1—DATA FOR 30% OLIVE OIL EMULSIONS. SEPECIFIC AREA AND SEPARATION OF OIL AT VARIOUS INTERVALS OF TIME

Specific area in sq. cm/g oil (all values $\times 10^3$)

Emulsion no.	Agents	Immediately	After			
			3/7 week	1 week	2 weeks	3 weeks
99	0.5% Sodium sulphide	13.52 (nil)	1.80 (20.0)	0.88 (24.0)	Broken	
100	0.5% Sodium sulphide + .1% Dhak gum	13.12 (nil)	7.25 (8.5)	1.48 (21.5)	0.51 (26.0)	Broken
101	0.5% Sodium sulphide + .1% Bel gum	13.73 (nil)	5.28 (15.0)	2.85 (20.5)	0.95 (25.0)	Broken
102	0.5% Sodium sulphide + .1% Katira gum	11.11 (nil)	Broken			
103	1.0% Sodium sulphide	13.68 (nil)	7.38 (8.5)	1.48 (24.0)	0.94 (25.0)	Broken
104	1.0% Sodium sulphide + .1% Dhak gum	13.61 (nil)	9.66 (8.0)	1.96 (20.0)	0.66 (26.0)	Broken
105	1.0% Sodium sulphide + .1% Bel gum	13.78 (nil)	4.87 (7.0)	2.63 (21.0)	1.08 (25.0)	Broken
106	1.0% Sodium sulphide + .1% Katira gum	11.69 (nil)	Broken			
107	0.5% Potassium sulphide	13.38 (nil)	1.61 (22.5)	Broken		
108	0.5% Potassium sulphide + .1% Dhak gum	13.64 (nil)	4.58 (14.5)	1.51 (21.0)	Broken	
109	0.5% Potassium sulphide + .1% Bel gum	12.21 (nil)	4.77 (14.0)	1.60 (20.0)	Broken	
110	0.5% Potassium sulphide + .1% Katira gum	12.40 (nil)	Broken			
111	1.0% Potassium sulphide	13.73 (nil)	1.50 (22.5)	Broken		
112	1.0% Potassium sulphide + .1% Dhak gum	13.55 (nil)	5.00 (14.0)	1.92 (20.5)	Broken	
113	1.0% Potassium sulphide + .1% Bel gum	12.68 (nil)	5.64 (12.0)	2.00 (20.0)	Broken	
114	1.0% Potassium sulphide + .1% Katira gum	12.87 (nil)	Broken			

(Quantities in parenthesis being the percentage oil separation on a particular day).

TABLE 2—DATA FOR 30% OLIVE OIL EMULSIONS

Emulsion no.	Agent	Graphically determined Initial specific area ($\sigma \times 10^3$)	Stability Coefficient ($K \times 10^3$)
99	0.5% Sodium sulphide	10.23	1.80
100	0.5% Sodium sulphide + .1% Dhak gum	11.48	3.37
101	0.5% Sodium sulphide + .1% Bel gum	12.02	4.15
102	0.5% Sodium sulphide + .1% Katira gum	10.72	0.56
103	1.0% Sodium sulphide	10.00	3.06
104	1.0% Sodium sulphide + .1% Dhak gum	10.72	3.69
105	1.0% Sodium sulphide + .1% Bel gum	10.00	4.04
106	1.0% Sodium sulphide + .1% Katira gum	11.75	1.03
107	0.5% Potassium sulphide	12.02	1.05
108	0.5% Potassium sulphide + .1% Dhak gum	11.48	2.65
109	0.5% Potassium sulphide + .1% Bel gum	12.02	2.55
110	0.5% Potassium sulphide + .1% Katira gum	11.22	0.19
111	1.0% Potassium sulphide	13.80	1.21
112	1.0% Potassium sulphide + .1% Dhak gum	11.48	3.08
113	1.0% Potassium sulphide + .1% Bel gum	11.22	3.22
114	1.0% Potassium sulphide + .1% Katira gum	13.80	0.48

Harkins, Davis and Clark⁵ pointed out that the stability of emulsion particles seems to be brought about by the orientation of molecules at the interface. These investigators mention the fact that the orientation of molecules at the interface between the dispersed particle and the dispersion medium is such that the molecules fit the curvature of the droplet. Harkins⁴ assumed that the type of emulsion (o/w or w/o) formed depends upon the orientation and packing of the molecules of the emulsifier at the interface.

The molecules of the emulsifying soap which might be formed due to interaction of, K^+ , or Na^+ ions with the oleate ions of free oleic acid present in olive oil, would be so oriented that polar group, $COONa$ or $COOK$ is in water and the hydrocarbon chain in oil. He further states that if the cross sectional area of the terminal atom of the polar group, in this case the metal atom is greater than that of the hydrocarbon chain, then the water surface of the adsorbed film will necessarily be greater than the oil surface, i.e., the water will surround the oil and o/w type emulsion is obtained.

Further the type of emulsion formed between oil and water will depend upon the size of the metal atom. In case of sodium or potassium oleate the end $COONa$ dips into water while the hydrocarbon end will be submerged in the oil. The film is convex on the water side. Thus oil in water type of emulsion is favoured.

The particle size of the emulsion produced can be related to the dimensions of the adsorbed emulsifier molecule, other factors remaining constant. In case of o/w type of emulsion the larger the polar group, the greater will be the concavity of the oriented layer in the oil side and smaller the droplet.

The small size of globules of potassium sulphide emulsion and emulsions produced with the combination of this substance with different gums can also be explained on the basis of Harkins and Keith's⁶ oriented wedge theory. The metal atoms in soaps

of Na and K increase in size in the order in which the metals are listed. According to the orientation theory, this indicates that potassium atom being larger than sodium, potassium oleate should give rise to smaller particles than sodium oleate. Ability of soaps of K and Na to emulsify oil in water should decrease in this order.

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